

TREAT-AD

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Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enablement Resource

INPP5D (SHIP1) Screening

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Introduction

Src Homology 2-containing Inositol 5'- Phosphatase-1 (SHIP-1), encoded by *INPP5D*, is selectively expressed in brain microglia.¹ SHIP-1 plays a critical negative role in triggering receptor expressed on myeloid cells 2 (TREM2) signaling pathway,² which promotes the optimal microglial function required to attenuate AD progression.³ Increased expression of SHIP-1 in brain has been associated with late-onset Alzheimer' Disease, the most common form of Alzheimer' Disease (AD).⁴ However, the detailed role of SHIP-1 in AD onset and progression remains unclear. Although several small molecules have been reported to modulate SHIP-1, the lack of efficacy in advanced models highly limited these compounds as potential therapeutics or probes for biological studies.⁵ To address this critical need, we developed and implemented a high-throughput screen platform to explore new chemotypes that modulate SHIP-1 catalytic domain activity. We screened 93,516 diverse small molecules sourced from commercial vendors using a malachite green-based assay for anti-SHIP-1 activity. Through analysis, prioritization, and validation of the screening hits, we identified 3 types of novel scaffolds that inhibit SHIP-1 phosphatase domain with IC₅₀s as low as 16.8 μM.

Screening Strategy

We first optimized the previously reported PtdIns(3,4,5)P₃-diC₈ malachite green coupled assay⁶ for the use in 384-well plates. An "excellent-range" Z' score of 0.84 was determined for the assay. Subsequently, nearly 95,000 compounds were screened in order to identify potential scaffolds for lead development. To

accomplish this, first a virtual screen was performed against the catalytic site of SHIP-1 and the compounds contained within Purdue's compound collection. The library plates with the highest scoring compounds from the virtual screen were chosen for the initial 50,176 compound HT screen. An additional 43,340 compounds were within the CNS-biased libraries within Purdue's compound collection then were screened. All compounds were screened at 10 μ M with the catalytic domain of SHIP-1, which should bias the screen to identify active site (i.e. orthosteric) inhibitors.

SHIP-1 and SHIP-2 protein purification:

The catalytic domains of human SHIP-1 and SHIP-2 were cloned into the pET-21a vector. The catalytic domain construct used for SHIP-1 was from 397-715 amino acid residues. The catalytic domain used for SHIP-2 was from 420-732 amino acid residues. The proteins were purified in Rosetta DE3 BL21 cells. The cells were grown at 37°C (while shaking at 200rpm) until the OD was reached between 0.6-0.8. Next, protein production was induced using 0.5mM IPTG. The protein induction was carried out for 20 hours at 18°C (while shaking at 180rpm). Then the bacterial cells were harvested by centrifugation at 5500 rpm for 15 minutes. The bacterial pellet was dissolved in 20mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 500mM NaCl pH 7 with 1mM PMSF. Next, the cells were lysed through sonication. The cell lysate was then centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 30 minutes to remove cell debris. The supernatant was incubated with Ni-NTA resin (Qiagen). The standard affinity purification protocol was followed using the Qiagen handbook. The protein elution was concentrated using Millipore Amicon Ultra centrifugal filter device. The purified protein was stored in 20mM HEPES, 300mM NaCl pH 7. The purity of the purified protein was assessed using a SDS PAGE gel. The purified protein was then aliquoted and flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored in -80°C.

The SHIP-1 catalytic domain purified protein was run on a SDS PAGE and stained with Gel Code Blue (Figure 1A). The SHIP-2 catalytic domain purified protein was run on a SDS PAGE and stained with Gel Code Blue (Figure 1B). The SHIP-1 catalytic domain had a very low yield since the protein was insoluble and the majority was in the pellet (insoluble fraction). Around 12-20L of bacterial culture was necessary to obtain around 3-4mg of protein. Additionally, we found that autoinduction at 18°C yielded the best soluble protein expression. Since the His-Ni Column elution was not pure, a downstream ion exchange column (HiTrapQHP) and a size exclusion column (S75 or S200) were run to get protein more than 90% purity. The SHIP-2 catalytic domain was much more soluble and had a higher yield of around 10mg of protein per L of LB. The purified protein was then used to characterize its kinetic activity using PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 as the substrate.

Figure 1. Purification of SHIP-1 and SHIP-2 protein. A. Purification flow of SHIP-1 catalytic domain. After His-Ni Column, the elution was used to run an ion exchange column (HiTrapQ HP) followed by size exclusion chromatography S75. B. Purification flow of SHIP-2 catalytic domain. The protein was concentrated after His-Ni Column.

High Throughput Screening Protocol:

The single point inhibition rates were obtained by using PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 as a substrate at 25 °C in pH7.4 HEPES buffer(150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂). Compounds were pre-transferred to 384-well plates by Echo 550 liquid handler (Labcyte)(10 μM final concentration). 10 μL of PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 solution was added to each well. The reaction was then initiated by adding 25 μL of the enzyme solution. The final reaction concentrations for compounds, PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8, and the enzyme are 10 μM, 45 μM, and 50 nM correspondingly. The reaction was quenched after 5 min by the addition of 40 μL of Malachite green reagent (Biomol, PA, USA). And then the plates were incubated for another 25 min at room temperature. Absorbance at 620 nm was measured using a SpectraMax Plus 384 Microplate Reader (Molecular Devices, LLC, USA). The inhibition rates for the compounds were calculated.

HTS results:

As summarized in Table 1, 208 primary hits were identified that inhibited SHIP-1's catalytic activity >50% and were designated as Tier 1 hits. An additional 376 primary hits were identified that inhibited SHIP-1's activity >30%, but less than 50% and were designated as Tier 2 hits. The Tier 1 hits were prioritized and subjected to cheminformatics analyses that eliminated compounds with substructures found within the PAINS databases, are known promiscuous binders, and/or strong electrophiles such as Michael acceptors. Next, hits with similar structures were grouped into series with a total of 16 hit series identified from the Tier 1 hits. Next, 70 compounds encompassing the original hits and closely related analogues were purchased. Their structure and purity were confirmed by LC-MS and their ability to inhibit SHIP-1 was confirmed. Of the 16 hit series, 8 reproduced their inhibitory activity at 100 μM (Figure 2A).

Library ID	Number of tier 1 hits	Number of tier 2 hits
ACM1K	23	37
ACN5K	10	15
CB_30K	0	0
CB_50K	8	28
CB_Fragment	0	0
CB_GPCR	0	0
CB_ION	0	0
CB_Kinase	0	0
CB_NHR	0	0
CBm_20K_CNS	33	37
CBm_30K_DIVERSET	0	3
CD_10K	1	2
CD_60K	14	47
ChemBridge43K	31	77
ChemDiv55K	43	97
CNS_ChemDiv	8	20
CNS_Enamine	1	0
CNS_LC	3	3
CNS_OTAVA	0	0
CNS_TimTec	3	2
LC_50K	0	0
LC_CP_29K_m	0	0
LC_Fragment_PPI	0	0
LC_Fragment_Sol	0	0
LOPAC2016	6	9
SP2400	26	41

Table 1. HTS hits identified from each compound library. Define: Tier 1 hits >50% inhibition at 10 μ M Concentration; Tier 2 hits = 30% ~50% inhibition at 10 μ M Concentration

Figure 2. Compound's structures of HTS hits. A. Representative compounds' structures in the 8 series of HTS hits that reproduce inhibitory activity at 100 μM . B. Structures of 3 series of compounds with their IC_{50} s.

Hit Validation

To determine if any of these hit series exerted their inhibitory effects through an aggregation mechanism, a common but undesirable mode of action, their IC_{50} values against SHIP-1 was measured in the presence and absence of the detergent Triton X-100. For five of these series, their inhibitory activity was significantly abolished by the addition of the detergent. The C4, C10, and C12 series of compounds were unaffected (Figure 2B). Furthermore, the compounds in these 3 series showed clear inhibitory selectivity of SHIP-1 over SHIP-2, which are close paralogs in the inositol 5'-Phosphatase (SHIP) enzyme family. Therefore, these 3 series were advanced to the MCCB core for retrosynthetic analysis, structure-activity-relationship (SAR) studies, and derivation.

SHIP-1(Catalytic Domain=Ptase) IC_{50} test protocol:

Buffer: 50 mM HEPES Buffer (pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl_2). Substrate: 1-(1,2-dioctanoylphosphatidyl)inositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate, tetrasodium salt (Cayman Chemical, Item No. 10007764). The IC_{50} values of the inhibitors were assayed using $\text{PtdIns}(3,4,5)\text{P}_3\text{-diC}_8$ as a substrate at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$ in pH7.4 HEPES buffer(150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl_2). The compounds were series diluted in 96-well plates and give compound solutions with final concentrations ranging from 1 μM to 100 μM . Then 25 μL of

PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 solution was added. The reaction was initiated by adding 25 μ L of the enzyme solution. The final reaction concentrations for PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 and the enzyme are 45 μ M and 50 nM correspondingly. The reaction was quenched after 5 min by the addition of 200 μ L of Malachite green reagent (Biomol, PA, USA). And then the plates were incubated for another 25 min at room temperature. Absorbance at 620 nm was measured using a SpectraMax Plus 384 Microplate Reader (Molecular Devices, LLC, USA). IC₅₀ values for the compounds were calculated by fitting the absorbance at 620 nm versus inhibitor concentration.

Detergent Assay (weed out aggregators) Protocol:

Buffer: 50 mM HEPES Buffer (pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 0.01% Triton X-100).

Substrate: 1-(1,2-dioctanoylphosphatidyl)inositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate, tetrasodium salt (Cayman Chemical, Item No. 10007764). The IC₅₀ values of compounds were determined by using PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 as a substrate at 25 °C in 50 mM HEPES Buffer (pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 0.01% Triton X-100). The compounds were series diluted in 96-well plates and give compound solutions (50 μ L). Then 25 μ L of PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 solution was added. The reaction was initiated by adding 25 μ L of the enzyme solution. The final reaction concentrations for PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 and the enzyme are 30 μ M and 100 nM correspondingly. The reaction was quenched after 4 min by adding 200 μ L of Malachite BioMol Green (Enzo Lifesciences, PA, USA). And then the plates were incubated for another 25 min at room temperature. Absorbance at 620 nm was measured using a SpectraMax Plus 384 Microplate Reader (Molecular Devices, LLC, USA). IC₅₀ values for the compounds were calculated by fitting the absorbance at 620 nm versus inhibitor concentration.

SHIP-2 (Catalytic Domain=Ptase) IC₅₀ (Counter-Screen) protocol:

Buffer: 50 mM HEPES Buffer (pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂). Substrate: 1-(1,2-dioctanoylphosphatidyl)inositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate, tetrasodium salt (Cayman Chemical, Item No. 10007764). The IC₅₀ values of compounds were determined by using PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 as a substrate at 25 °C in 50 mM HEPES buffer (pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂). The compounds were series diluted in 96-well plates and give compound solutions (50 μ L). Then 25 μ L of PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 solution was added. The reaction was initiated by adding 25 μ L of the enzyme solution. The final reaction concentrations for PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 and the enzyme are 30 μ M and 100 nM correspondingly. The reaction was quenched after 4 min by adding 200 μ L of Malachite BioMol Green (Enzo Lifesciences, PA, USA). And then the plates were incubated for another 25 min at room temperature. Absorbance at 620 nm was measured using a SpectraMax Plus 384 Microplate Reader (Molecular Devices, LLC, USA). IC₅₀ values for the compounds were calculated by fitting the absorbance at 620 nm versus inhibitor concentration.

Cell-Based Assays:

The validated HTS hits were evaluated for their ability to promote phagocytosis in microglia cells. The compounds were tested in both human microglial clone 3 cell line (HMC3) and murine microglial cell line BV-2. The compound TAD-0058583 showed an EC₅₀ of 9.9 μ M on enhancing phagocytosis in BV-2 cells, while other experimental trials resulted in trivial or no activity. At concentrations that promote phagocytosis, the inhibitor was non-toxic at 48 hours. These data showed early evidence that the inhibitor can promote human microglia-like cell phagocytosis.

pHrodo-myelin phagocytosis/cell viability assay with microglial cells:

The 384-well plate high content assay with BV2 and HMC3 immortalized microglial cell lines is developed to quantify phagocytosis and cell viability simultaneously. BV2 and HMC3 cells are culture with DMEM GlutaMax media (ThermoFisher) contains 10% FBS and Pen-Strep in 37°C 5% CO₂ incubator. Compound stocks are 20mM in DMSO stored in -20°C or -80°C freezer. The assay is also used with primary microglia isolated from mouse brain, only difference is cell plated at 2000 cell/45ul/well into 384 well plate. Following are assay procedures, all liquid handling steps are performed with automatic system, the OPENTRONS OT2 system is used in the lab.

Day 1: Cells are plated in 384-well plates (Corning Falcon 384 well Optilux Black and clear bottom plates, or similar plates for cellular imaging) with BV2 at 400 cells/45ul/well and HMC3 at 600 cells/45ul/well in.

Day 2: Cells are treated with compounds for total 48 hours. For treating cells, 10x compounds serial dilutions are prepared. Typically starting well with adding 3 ul of the 20mM stock into 97 ul media resulted in 600uM and 3% DMSO that will be serial diluted in 1:3 (transfer and mix 30ul to next well with 60ul media containing 3% DMSO) in 96 well compound plate, total 10 points. Transfer 5ul/well of the 10x compounds to cell plates with 45ul/well cells resulted in dose range of 60uM to 3nM 10 points treatments. Duplicates of each compound treatment are regularly performed with the 384 well assay. Cell plates are then returned to the 37C incubator.

Day 3: Cells are seeded with pHrodo-myelin (for total 20 hours) 24 hours after starting compound treatment. The pHrodo-myelin stocks are at 1mg/ml (protein equivalent) stored in -20°C or -80°C freezer, thaw a stock and dilution of the stock with culture media into 10x seeding solution (50ug/ml), and adding 5ul/well to 384 well cell plate, seeded plates are returned to the 37°C incubator.

Day 4: Stain cell with Hoechst-33342 and imaging. Prepare the nuclear staining solution with adding 1ul of 10mM Hoechst-33342 to every 1ml culture media that will be added to cell plate at 20ul/well, the final concentration of Hoechst-33342 to cells is at about 2.5ug/ml. Incubate cell plates for >30 min in the 37°C incubator before imaging.

Cell plates are scanned with ArrayScan automatic high content imaging system using a 10x objective lens, 4 fields/well are collected. Three measurements are extracted from the assay, 1) phagocytosis signal by mean total phagocytosis spot intensity per cell, 2) total cell counts per well as the main measurement of cell viability, and 3) mean average nuclear intensity per cell as profiling of cell health since apoptotic cells showing nuclear intensity increase (early apoptosis) and decrease (later apoptosis) respectively.

Data analysis: Mean of untreated controls are calculate for normalization. Raw data are normalized to controls, %phagocytosis is calculated with $100 \times (X - \text{Min}) / (\text{Max} - \text{Min})$, where the X is raw data from a well, Min is mean from control unseeded wells and Max is mean from control pHrodo-myelin seeded wells. Cell counts and nuclear intensity are % of untreated wells respectively. Normalized data are analyzed with the Prism software for dose response curve fitting and potency determination.

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